

Public Perceptions & Attitudes Towards Prisoner Disenfranchisement in England and Wales

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Abstract

The disenfranchisement of prisoners is a contentious debate within the court of public opinion. Despite longstanding controversy, there has been little in the way of study into the public opinions and attitudes towards prisoners accessing their 'protected' human rights; the right to vote and the right to marry. This paper explores whether contextualised information surrounding the interpersonal characteristics of prisoners holds any influence over public opinions and attitudes as to whether it is appropriate to strip prisoners of their human rights. Although previous research has explored public views on prisoner disenfranchisement, it fails to understand how individual prisoner circumstances can influence public views in relation to access to their rights. Purpose-built vignettes were created to investigate whether public opinions and attitudes towards prisoner rights hold up in practice, and to understand whether certain characteristics hold more weight than others. Although the public sample (N=53) displayed opinions supporting the enfranchisement of prisoners, the results from the contextualised vignettes displayed that the interpersonal characteristics of prisoners were more influential when applying these opinions in practice. This paper identifies that the contextualisation of prisoners as individuals does hold influence over public opinion towards prisoner disenfranchisement. However, this cannot be applied as a one-size-fits-all approach. Each interpersonal characteristic was found to hold different weighting within each human right explored and these findings were further considered within the age, gender, and occupation of the sample base. The findings of this study shed light onto the ongoing controversy and debate surrounding prisoner disenfranchisement and establish the importance of interpersonal characteristics of prisoners in settling the public discourse surrounding prisoner rights.

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Chapter 1: Introduction & Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

Prisoner disenfranchisement can take many forms: loss of voting rights, loss of marriage rights, loss of privileges. In England and Wales, prisoners have suffered from disenfranchisement since the creation of the first built prisons in the 19th century (Thorne and White, 2015). Despite major cultural, social, and legal reforms to the criminal justice system (CJS), disenfranchisement is a punishment that many serving prisoners still face. Large amounts of public and political discourse lie at the centre of prisoner disenfranchisement which often leads to polarising public views on prisoner rights (Dhami and Cruise, 2013). As prisoners are often portrayed as a homogenous group, individualised characteristics are ignored in favour of viewing prisoners as a ‘dangerous other’ (Drake, 2011). These portrayals can negatively influence the opinions and attitudes of the public (Marsh, 2009), which in turn decreases support for the protection of prisoner rights.

While existing literature has explored public opinion on different aspects of prisoner disenfranchisement, a gap persists in understanding if interpersonal contextualised information on prisoners can influence these opinions. This dissertation aims to bridge this gap by investigating how individual prisoner context influences public views of prisoner rights, and if specific characteristics are more influential than others. This dissertation aims to explore these ideas by answering the following research questions:

1. What are public perspectives and opinions regarding prisoner rights in England and Wales?
2. Are these attitudes maintained in practice when given contextualised details about prisoners?
3. Do specific characteristics of prisoners’ influence opinions towards prisoner rights?

The prisoner rights chosen for this study are the right to vote and the right to marriage. As set out in the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) (2022) these are both protected human rights in the UK. Building on previous literature that evidences a multitude of issues lie at the centre of prisoner disenfranchisement, this study aims to focus on how the loss of these rights for prisoners are viewed by members of the public, and if these opinions can be changed. This research has important implications for current and proposed policy and highlights the importance of viewing prisoners as individuals.

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Introduction

An extensive review into prisoner rights literature, policy, and judicial outcomes was conducted for this dissertation. This review begins by contextualising the history of prisoner disenfranchisement, with focus remaining on the right to vote and the right to marriage. These rights are protected by the ECHR and Human Rights Act 1998 however, it is often found that prisoners are exempt from this protection. Current and proposed policy in the UK is then discussed with reference to international legislation. There is no international guidance in relation to the implementation of prisoner rights, which leads to conflicting structures and the common involvement of human rights governance.

The formation of public opinion will then be explored, with particular reference to forming opinions on prisoner rights. Alongside this, the theoretical basis of Othering will be applied. Viewing prisoners as a homogenous group can feed into an anti-prisoner rhetoric that is prevalent in political discourse and media coverage, which in-turn impacts the formation of public opinion. Exploring this idea further, the influence of interpersonal characteristics of prisoners was examined in relation to public views on prisoner rights.

As this dissertation aims to understand the significance individual prisoner characteristics have on public views on prisoner rights policy, this theoretical and academic basis is key. Overall, this dissertation poses the overarching question: Prisoner rights or human rights?

1.2.2 History of prisoner voting rights

The origin of a prisoners 'civic death' (Liberty Human Rights, 2016, p.5) is an unintended consequence of imprisonment and 19th-century voting laws. The right to vote in England was officially legislated in

the Representation of the People Act 1918 which combated a voting system rife with misogyny and classism (Liberty Human Rights, 2016). Prior to this legislation, the pre-requisite for voting eligibility was based on land ownership, wealth, and gender. However, individuals who had committed a criminal offence and imprisoned were legally stripped of any land or property as a further punishment (UK Parliament, 2024), meaning they were no longer eligible to vote in political elections (Liberty Human Rights, 2016). Prisoner's losing their right to vote was coined as a 'collateral consequence' of imprisonment by Dhami and Cruise (2013, p.211). Despite the origins of prisoner disenfranchisement, the voting ban for prisoners remained unchallenged until the case of *Hirst v UK* in 2005 (Table 1).

Table 1 – Timeline of *Hirst vs UK* (2005)

In 2005 it was officially ruled that the legislative ban on prisoner voting rights in England and Wales was in violation of the ECHR Article 3 of Protocol 1: the right to free elections (House of Commons, 2023; European Court of Human Rights, 2022a). The UK was under strict obligation to comply with this ruling (House of Commons, 2023) which fuelled political and public hostility towards prisoner rights (Scott, 2013; Easton, 2013). The British government decided a public consultation was beneficial to understand public views on the matter and utilise results to develop new legislation to solve this issue (Thorne and White, 2015; Dhami and Cruise, 2013). However, this consultation had serious methodological shortcomings. Public response was minimal showing only 88 respondents from the first consultation, of which 40 were members of the public. The responses led to the basis of the current legislative changes and the closure of *Hirst vs UK* in 2018 (Johnson, 2023; Horne and White, 2015). By implementing nation-wide legislation from a public consultation with 40 responses from the public, it fails to ascertain whether the change to prisoner voting rights matches with a realistic public view. Non-government agencies were also very critical of this approach. Prisoner rights charities criticised the moral and legal repercussions of the continuation of prisoner disenfranchisement (Prison Reform Trust, 2011). The updated legislation now allows a

specific group of prisoners to vote: unconvicted, convicted but not yet sentenced, civil prisoners, and those released on temporary licence (ROTL) (Prison Reform Trust, 2023).

1.2.3 Current prisoner voting rights

After the revision to the Representation of the People Act in 2018, it was the first time in UK history that prisoners had access to their right to vote (Liberty Human Rights, 2016). However, Davies and Jones (2023) studied the application of the revised policy across prisons in England and found administrative shortcomings that have rendered the revised policy almost useless. A lack of prison facilities that could allow prisoners to engage in their newfound right and confusions about eligibility were prevalent in their findings. Previous studies have found only half of prisoners are aware of their voting rights (Dhami and Cruise, 2013), and with the implementation of new changes, it is likely this number will decrease.

To combat any misinformation or confusion, mandatory guidance of the new voting regulations was implemented by the Ministry of Justice to all prisons in England and Wales (2020). This guidance includes permanently displaying an information poster at the prison reception (Figure 1) and informing the prisoner of their voting rights upon arrival (Ministry of Justice, 2020). However, a key weakness in the implementation of this guidance is the extreme emotional distress that an individual can feel when first entering prison (HM Inspectorate, 2015). Thus, informing prisoners about their voting rights upon arrival is seemingly peripheral compared to the issues prisoners are facing such as overcrowding, violence, and lack of medical care (Easton, 2013). The administrative system for prisoners to understand, question, or access their right to vote is extremely limited which can cause 'administrative disenfranchisement' (Davies and Jones, 2023, p.1). Without sufficient plans to alter these policies or implement supportive considerations, it clearly displays the government's stance of prisoners 'legal incapacity' (Johnson, 2024, p.6) to access their right to vote.

What are my voting rights?

Convicted prisoners serving a custodial sentence are disqualified from voting while they are detained in custody. This has been made clear on the warrant of committal since July 2018. However, some people in prison may have the right to vote, in certain circumstances.

You may be eligible to vote if:

- ✓ You are an unconvicted prisoner.
- ✓ You are a convicted but unsentenced prisoner.
- ✓ You are a civil prisoner.
- ✓ You are serving a default term for non-payment of a fine.
- ✓ You have been committed to prison for contempt of court.
- ✓ You are in the community on home detention curfew (HDC) or released on temporary licence (ROTL).*

*Prisoners on HDC and ROTL are only eligible to register to vote once they are in the community and become ineligible again upon return to prison.

If you wish to make an application to register to vote, or are unsure about whether or not you can vote, please speak to a member of staff and read the guidance within the *Restrictions on Prisoner Voting* policy framework.

Staff can print out voting registration forms from the staff intranet:
<https://intranet.noms.gsi.gov.uk/support/offender-services/prisoner-voting>

Your eligibility to vote will still depend on whether you are on the electoral register. It remains the legal responsibility of your Electoral Registration Officer to determine applications to register to vote based on the facts of each case. This can be reviewed on an ongoing basis.

Figure 1 – Ministry of Justice (2020)

If a prisoner is eligible to vote there are certain parameters that can inhibit their ability to exercise their right. The Voter Identification Regulations 2022 states that when registering to vote an individual needs certain documentation and a fixed address. This can be difficult for prisoners to procure, especially in uncontrollable situations i.e. they have lost their documentation whilst in prison (Davies and Jones, 2023). Rules within this legislation further state an individual must be outside of prison to register to vote (Ministry of Justice, 2020).

However, prisoners are not eligible for release with the specific purpose to vote, and they cannot use the address of the prison when registering (Davies and Jones, 2023; Ministry of Justice, 2020). Furthermore, those on ROTL are only able to vote once they have been re-integrated into society and 'are in the community and become ineligible again to return to prison' (Ministry of Justice, 2020, p.4). Fulfilling these criteria can be difficult and confusing which can lead to some prisoners not partaking in their voting rights. Low numbers of prisoner voting have often been used in arguments for the disenfranchisement of prisoners (Jones and Davies, 2022). Therefore, ensuring that those eligible do engage with their voting rights could increase the chances for prisoner rights to be protected. However, due to the current system being complicated and inaccessible to many prisoners, it feeds into the rhetoric of prisoners not *caring* about this right rather than the *inaccessible* nature of the system.

Similarly, The Prison Reform Trust (2001, cited in Dhami, 2005) emphasised the importance of prisoner enfranchisement as pivotal to continuing a true national democracy. They detailed an English constituency during the 1997 General election in which a Conservative candidate won the majority by 77 votes. However, this area housed nearly 1,500 disenfranchised prisoners, thus, if all prisoners were given the right to vote it could have held a major turning point for the political outcome of this constituency. With over 95,000 people currently imprisoned in England and Wales (Sturge, 2023) it conveys the political power that prisoners could hold if added to the electoral register (Sturge and Carthew, 2023). The denial of prisoner voting rights conveys a governmental level of disinterest towards prisoners' political views, and consequently, prisoners will be less inclined to get involved in political matters in a democracy that does not 'recognise the prisoner as a citizen' (Easton, 2013, p.489; Dhami, 2005; Jones and Davies, 2022).

Many scholars suggest that the modern continuation of prisoner disenfranchisement is legal and moral justifications viewing it as *punishment* for law breaking behaviour (Easton, 2013; Dhami and Cruise, 2013; Davies and Jones, 2023). However, this can question the purposes of prison as a consequence for offending behaviour in a modern society. In a Ministry of Justice Prison Strategy whitepaper (2021), it states that the purpose of prison is to 'protect the public... tackle the underlying causes of offending, and promote rehabilitation and reform to reduce reoffending' (p.5). The removal of prisoner voting liberties doesn't aid these specific prison purposes set out by the Ministry of Justice (2021) and in some cases it has been shown to work against these purposes (Dhami, 2005; Dhami and Cruise, 2013). It suggests that there may be an intentional significance behind the continuation of prisoner disenfranchisement. Dhami and Cruise (2012) explain this phenomenon as an 'invisible punishment' (p.211), an unrecognised prisoner experience that isn't directly related to the main initiatives of prison as a penal sanction. An invisible punishment can range from deterioration of personal relationships to the removal of voting rights once imprisoned (Dhami and Cruise, 2012). The invisible punishments endured by prisoners are infringing on their democratic rights, and consequently, prisoners are becoming more disconnected from their government and rejected by the public (Jones and Davies, 2022). This further reaffirms physical and social isolation that prisoners go through during their sentence (Dhami, 2005).

1.2.4 International laws

Exploring international solutions to prisoner voting discourse displays the legal and moral hypocrisy at the centre of prisoner disenfranchisement. In research focusing on international responses to prisoner voting rights, Dhami and Cruise (2013) found that global prisoner disenfranchisement falls across a

'continuum' (p.213). Internationally, some prisoners have full access to their voting rights e.g. South Africa (SA), some partial only consequential to their offence type or sentence length e.g. Australia, and some completely deprived of their rights e.g. USA (Uggen and Manza, 2002). Similarly to the UK, countries such as Australia and SA had action demanded for their prisoner voting legislation due to infringements on human rights conventions (Australian Human Rights Commission, 2010; South African Human Rights Commission, 2003).

Both countries took varying actions; Australian state law now allows prisoner voting dependent upon sentence length (Hill, 2009), and SA has full prisoner enfranchisement (De Vos, 2004). However, after the implementation of these changes, a lack of attention to the compulsory electoral enrolment seemed to occur within prisons across both countries. This was shown when only two prisoners from one of Australia's largest prisons undertook their civil voting right during the 2013 Federal Election (Justice Action, 2021). Moreover, the government's decision to remove the prisoner voting ban in SA inevitably came under scrutiny, and many cases were put against the Constitutional Court to remand this legislation, but none since have been successful in their endeavour (De Vos, 2004). Differential international legislation and laws surrounding prisoner disenfranchisement show the struggles faced at each end of the prisoner voting continuum. It is important to ensure when tackling this issue that a multifaceted approach is taken, encompassing the political climates, public opinions, and legislation are cooperative in order to protect prisoners democratic and civil rights (Owers, 2006).

1.2.5 Marriage rights

Prisoner rights discourse in the UK encompasses more than just voting rights. As this study is exploring prisoners' loss of rights it is imperative to expand the focus to other rights that are being withheld from prisoners. One example is the right to marriage. Article 12 of the ECHR guarantees the right to marry (2022b), and currently all prisoners in England and Wales can engage in this right and are protected by the Marriage Act 1983. However, there is currently a proposed government Bill that is attempting to remove this right, the Victims and Prisoners Bill (2023). Section 48 of the Bill prohibits life sentenced prisoners from getting married by amending the Marriage Act 1983 to legally ban life sentenced prisoners from marriage. As this Bill is in the pathway to becoming an Act, an Impact Assessment (IA) was published by the Ministry of Justice (2023). The main acknowledgements were the 'social or religious impact' (p.2) onto connecting parties, such as a partner or child from the intended marriage. Thus, if this Bill is passed to an Act there are clear infringements on the right to marriage for the *spouse* as well as the prisoner. Utilising key findings in the support of prisoner disenfranchisement, the removal of rights is often justified as a further punishment for offending behaviours (Dhami and Cruise, 2013).

However, applying this rationale to removing the right to marriage, it becomes incompatible as marriage encompasses more than just the individual prisoner.

Delving into the justification for the removal of marriage rights for life sentenced prisoners, a government-wide ‘concern that allowing the marriage or civil partnership of whole life prisoners undermines public confidence in the Criminal Justice System’ (p.5) was the main incentive behind this section of the Bill. Mirroring previous findings, the justification behind prisoner-based policy is fulfilling a public confidence criterion rather than prioritising the needs of the prisoners it directly impacts (Scott, 2013). Moreover, a very small percentage (0.075%) of the prison population put forward an application for marriage in 2022 (Ministry of Justice, 2023). This calls into question the necessity of implementing a policy that would purposely remove a right that is not often used by prisoners. Thus, the proposed evidence base for the removal of a prisoners right to marriage show the influence public confidence and opinions have on prisoner welfare on a governmental level.

1.2.6 The Influence of Othering

Being convicted and sentenced to time in prison is a physical representation of failing to meet the standards of a law-abiding society (Silvia, 2005). Drake (2011) describes a predisposed habitus viewing prisoners as a ‘dangerous other’ (p.1); individuals who cannot be changed and need to be locked away from society. The process of Othering is a theoretical construct whereby inferiority or rejection is placed onto an identification of a certain group, often an out-group member of society e.g. prisoners (Brons, 2015; Silvia, 2005). Silvia et al (2005) explains via the black-sheep effect (Marques and Paez, 1994) that social rejection often occurs based purely on a singular characteristic. Therefore, the Othering that impacts prisoners could be the social stigma of imprisonment. This type of othering is often found in media and social policy (Marsh, 2009) in which prisoners are stigmatised and treated as a homogenous group needing punishment. Consequently, the negative habitus and othering towards prisoners impacts unseen areas of prisoners’ lives (Dhami and Cruise, 2013). This then encourages a self-perpetuating cycle by reaffirming social rejection through social rejection.

In contrast, viewing the social rejection of prisoners to be caused solely by their identification with prison ignores the moral perceptions of their *behaviours* rather than their *identification* (Whitehead, 2018). Morality is the formation and judgement of behaviours, and certain behaviours can be deemed immoral and are therefore stigmatised (Paruzel-Czachura et al, 2023). Carvelho and Chamberlen (2017) argue that a strong sense of moral order is indicative of supporting punitive punishment. However, Maruna and King (2009) have found that these moral ideals are malleable. Thus, the social rejection

and othering faced by prisoners may be due to the immoral views of criminal behaviours, rather than the label of prisoner alone. However, regardless of origin, the negative othering and social rejection that prisoners face remains well established (Whitehead, 2018).

An example of negative othering that prisoners face is shown from the response to the legal case of *Napier vs Scotland* (2005). The Scottish Prison Service (SPS) was found to be in violation of the ECHR as several active Scottish prisons were found to have inhumane sanitation conditions. The case against the SPS was won by Napier, a former prisoner, which resulted in a mass pay-out totaling over £11 million to all those who suffered within these prison conditions (Whitty, 2011). Once the decision was publicly announced, the media painted the prisoners who accepted the pay-out in an extremely negative light. Portrayals of these prisoners were shown as: 'increasingly litigious and compensation minded and liable to raise trivial issues to obtain financial or other rewards' (Eastson, 2013, p. 484). Whitty (2011) commented on this phenomenon, suggesting that othering and negative portrayals of prisoners is often a risk management strategy attempting to retain public confidence.

Describing these prisoners as 'compensation minded' (Eastson, 2013, p. 484) trivializes the inhumane experiences they had to endure and individualises the wrongdoings of the SPS onto the prisoners. This example displays the othering of prisoners and underlying anti-prisoner rhetoric often found from the mass media (Marsh, 2009). Considering this, the current study attempts to explore if providing individualised context negates the negative othering of prisoners to the public, and if this impacts views on prisoner rights.

1.2.7 Formation of public opinions

One of the key research aims in this study is understanding public opinions on prisoner rights. However, before delving into the topic, it is important to understand how the public form opinions. A key factor in forming opinions is gathering an information base of a subject (Oskamp and Schulz, 2005). Marsh (2009) found that the main avenues for gathering information on prisons and prisoners are newspapers and television media. However, displays of inaccurate, inflated, or false information are rife across these types of media (Easton, 2013). Thus, gathering information from a distorted source can lead to opinions which misrepresent the actuality of the issue. Furthermore, content analysis of newspaper articles on the prisoner voting debate by McNulty et al (2014), found British newspapers were 'vilifying' (p.372) the idea of supporting prisoner enfranchisement. However, this study focused on right-wing newspapers, therefore this result is unsurprising as political hostility from the leading conservative government remained high during the prisoner voting rights debate of *Hirst vs UK* (Scott, 2013). These

findings represent that public knowledge is often built on misrepresented 'truths' and biased media which can sway public opinions on prisoner rights.

In contrast, sourcing biased information on prisoners is unavoidable. With on average 1 in every 629 people in the UK having been previously imprisoned, and a fewer number having visited a prison in their lifetime, a small number of people have first-hand experiences within prison walls (Sturge and Carthew, 2023). Roberts and Hough (2005) found that the public have a wide recognition of the use of prison as a judicial punishment. However, Marsh (2009) found that regardless of the understanding of prison in the penal system, there is a distinct lack of understanding of the daily lives of those imprisoned. This trend represents a 'paradox of imprisonment' (p.289): prison is the most widely recognised sanction yet remains the most unknown in nature (Roberts and Hough, 2005). Utilising the limitations from these studies, it was revealed that there was a general lack of understanding as to the reliability of public knowledge (Dhami and Cruise, 2013). Therefore, this study aims to investigate how accuracy of knowledge influences views on prisoner rights.

1.2.8 Prisoner characteristics

Previous research has found that extra-legal characteristics of offenders, such as the age of an offender, can impact sentencing decisions (Blowers and Doerner, 2013). To better understand the significance in personal characteristics of offenders in mitigating sentencing decisions, Belton and Dhami (2024) researched a variety of interpersonal characteristics of offenders and found a significant influence on sentencing decisions between all groups. The interpersonal characteristics of offenders were classified into three categories: past, present, and future. Utilising these findings, this section will explore interpersonal characteristic categories in relation to prisoners.

Exploring the extra-legal characteristic of age, Kramer and Ulmer (1995) pioneered in exploring how the age of an offender influenced sentencing decisions. They coined the term 'age-leniency effect' which explains that older offenders are disproportionately sentenced to shorter prison sentences compared to younger offenders. Blowers and Doerner (2013) replicated their study and found consistent results; older offenders (aged 50 and over) were significantly less likely to be sentenced to time in prison. However, further study found victim characteristics impacted these results. Offenders that harmed older victims were more likely to be approached with higher levels of punitiveness, regardless of offender age (Bensimon and Bodner, 2012). However, it must be considered that these studies were conducted in the USA, and their applicability to the prosecution service or social context

in England and Wales is unclear. Nonetheless, it displays that the characteristic of age is influential in decisions towards offenders.

Utilising Belton and Dhimi's (2024) categorisation, the past of an offender is shown by their criminal history. Individuals with multiple offences are often labelled as deviant and their recidivism is met with punitive attitudes from the public, media, and legislative system (Mungan, 2010). These punitive responses are often relayed through longer and harsher sentencing (Roberts, 1996). However, it is unclear if these punitive attitudes are maintained to their rights as a prisoner. Bushway et al (2011) found that offenders with multiple previous convictions need a crime-free period of approximately 20 years to be socially and legally 'redeemed' (p.28) from their criminal wrongdoings. Thus, the social and legal stigma faced by repeat offenders would suggest that the support of enfranchisement for repeat offenders would be low, however, this study aims to fill this research gap.

Belton and Dhimi (2024) suggest higher levels of punitive attitudes to certain offender characteristics may be due to failing a 'moral assessment' (p.208) of behaviour. Thus, the severity of a prisoner's crime can influence the public opinion and attitude towards the severity of their punishment. Violent crimes are often viewed as the most severe type of crime. Felson (2009) theorised this may be due to the nature of violent crimes encompassing both 'harm-doing' and 'rule-breaking' (p.2) elements. The public often have much stronger punitive views of punishment for violent offenders (Rossi and Berk, 1997). In relation to prisoner rights, these findings could suggest that a more severe criminal, e.g. a murderer, would elicit stronger punitive responses from the public.

Easton (2013) conducted an extensive public and political review of the Human Rights Act 1998 and found that a large portion of the public believed that prisoner rights, i.e. voting, should be 'earned through good behaviour and forfeited through misconduct' (p.489). The public belief that prisoners should have their rights controlled through behavioural incentive programmes (BIP) is a popular finding amongst prisoner rights academia (Easton, 2013; Roberts and Hough, 2005). BIPs are currently used within prisons in England and Wales and are conducted through the Incentives and Earned Privilege Scheme (IEPS, Figure 2) which was introduced in 1995 (Booth, 2020). However, the effectiveness of BIPs and the IEPS in prisons has shown mixed results. Elbers et al (2022) conducted a meta-analysis of prison BIP studies and found that the structure of programmes often ignores those with extra cognitive or physical needs, and labels those who aren't responsive to the programme as irresponsible or unwilling with their rehabilitative efforts. Therefore, if prisoner rights were added into a framework such as IEPS, it would not be suitable for all prisoners.

Incentives and Earned Privileges Scheme (Ministry of Justice, 2022)

Incentive level:	Games consoles	Access to private cash	In-cell tv	Higher paying jobs	Requirements
BASIC	✗	Convicted: £5.50 Unconvicted: £27.50	✗ Apart from those with exceptional circumstances	✗	Not abided by behaviour principles
STANDARD	✓ Only games consoles from a pre-determined list allowed	Convicted: £19.80 Unconvicted: £60.50	✓	✗	Adequately abided by behaviour principles
ENHANCED	✓	Convicted: £33 Unconvicted: £66	✓	✓ Priority in access to higher paying jobs	Consistently abided by behaviour principles to a high standard.

Figure 2 – Incentives and Earned Privileges Scheme (Ministry of Justice, 2020)

Chapter 2: Methodology

2.1 Introduction

This study aims to build on limitations and existing literature gaps to investigate public opinions and attitudes towards prisoner disenfranchisement in England and Wales, with reference to the right to vote and marriage. This study differs from others through a focus on the interpersonal characteristics of prisoners, and exploring the level of influence they hold over public opinions and attitudes on prisoner rights.

Data for this study was collected via an anonymous online survey. Purposely designed measures were created to better understand public opinions, attitudes, and Othering surrounding the prisoner rights discourse. This was completed using vignettes. Each vignette contained a description of a fictional prisoner and detailed a high or low level of a prisoner characteristics: age, number of prior convictions, behaviour in prison, severity of crime, and length of prison sentence. Utilising a convenience snowball sampling method, the sample consisted of 53 participants. The survey design contained a set of closed quantitative questions, descriptive prisoner vignettes, Likert scales, and supporting qualitative questions. Analysis of the data occurred through two routes; a dependant T-test was used to analyse the main body of quantitative data collected, and supporting qualitative data was thematically analysed via Braun and Clarke's (2006) 6-step thematic analysis. These analysis methods were chosen as they fit the repeated measures design of the study and their time saving capabilities (Field, 2013).

2.2 Sampling

One of the main research aims in this study is to investigate public opinion on prisoner rights, therefore, reaching a large sample pool was key. An online survey was decided as the most appropriate method for the aims of this study as this methodology allows for much larger sample sizes than traditional methods (Oskamp and Schulz, 2005). OnlineSurveys.ac.uk was used to create the survey (Appendix 8.1). Online surveys work within the remits of an undergraduate dissertation via their cost-effectiveness and timesaving characteristics (Braun et al, 2020). Alongside this, they offer the ability to gather rich data sets from the inclusion of both qualitative and quantitative questions (Braun et al, 2020). The present study captured 53 responses. Therefore, due to the small sample size, this study presents as a small-scale explanatory study towards public opinions on prisoner rights debates (Dhami and Cruise, 2013).

Participants were recruited via snowball convenience sampling. A link was posted to social media alongside asking classmates, friends, and family for their participation. By using this type of sampling, it increased the scope of potential participants and increased the chances of a more representative sample (Braun et al, 2020). However, it was considered that by using social media as the primary distribution of the survey, it could create a coverage bias from proportionally over-representing certain demographics (Lehdonvirta et al, 2020).

Non-identifying demographic data was collected within the survey to assess the potential impact that coverage bias would have on the results. The sample consisted of 60.4% females (N=32), and 39.6% males (N=21). Within the 2021 census, the UK had a population of 51% females and 49% males (Office for national statistics, 2023). This study displays an over- representation of female respondents compared to the general population. However, this was unsurprising as due to the snowball sampling technique, it displays the large population of female undergraduates in the social science disciplines (Honeycutt and Jussim, 2020). Future research efforts could rectify this issue by purposely targeting a larger sample base outside of social-science academia.

2.3 Measures

2.3.1 Opinions

To properly measure public opinion with relation to prisoner rights, the definition of *opinion* must be understood and operationalised. In social science, an opinion is often defined as equivalent to beliefs or judgements (Oskamp and Schulz, 2005). Thereby, this study aims to deductively measure public opinion with closed nominal questions. These opinions will then be used for later analysis (Bryman et al, 2012; Berinsky, 2017).

Questions such as, ‘Do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?’ and ‘Do you think that prisoners serving life sentences should be able to get married?’ were used as an assessor for underlying public opinions towards specific prisoner debates (Appendix 8.1). Each question had a pre-set response of ‘No’ or ‘Yes’. Attempting to counteract the constraints of these closed-answer questions, each closed-answer question had an optional text box in which participants were encouraged to expand on their previous answer (Bryman et al, 2012). By including qualitative components to the questionnaire, it will help provide insight into certain opinions, therefore aiding in a more comprehensive understanding of opinions on prisoner rights (Burnett, 2009; Braun et al, 2020).

2.3.2 Attitudes in practice

This study aims to explore whether attitudes towards prisoner rights are upheld within contextualised situations, and if specific prisoner characteristics are influential towards a particular attitude or opinion. Previous studies have shown that public attitudes towards prisoner rights are largely negative (Marsh, 2009; Roberts and Hough, 2005). This study will measure opinions and attitudes against a set of vignettes to test if certain prisoner characteristics induce a more pro- or anti-prisoner rights attitude from the public. Dhimi and Cruise's (2013) Attitudes to Prisoner Disenfranchisement Scale was used as a guide in the conceptualisation of the attitude scales within the survey. Specific measures that related to the topic of this study were adapted from the scale. Furthermore, an additional answer column was added to create a five-point Likert answer scale. This allows participants to express any neutral attitudinal positions from a '*neither agree nor disagree*' column, which helps to improve the reliability of findings (Sturgis et al, 2012).

To measure attitudes, it is important to specify the differentiation of *attitude* from *opinion*. In social sciences an attitude is defined as a dispositional response; less malleable and more complex than an opinion (Oskamp and Schulz, 2005). This study aims to investigate the reliability of public opinions in contextualised prisoner descriptions, thereby showing the *attitudinal response* of an opinion (Oskamp and Schulz, 2005). To differentiate this study from existing literature, vignettes were used to reduce othering that may occur due to the prisoners stigmatising status (Silvia et al, 2005). This also allows for the exploration of a relationship between certain characteristics and their influence on opinions towards prisoner rights (Brons, 2015).

2.3.3 Vignettes

One of the main aims within this study is exploring whether specific prisoner characteristics influence opinions towards prisoner rights. Within this study, this was conducted using vignettes; carefully constructed scenarios used to assess attitudes and behaviours (Anguinis and Bradley, 2014). 10 purpose-made descriptive vignettes were created for this study. The content of each vignette detailed a fictional prisoner, including their convicted crime, sentence length, and a brief background of the offense. Each vignette was followed by the same three questions asking the participant their opinion on the prisoner's access for voting, marriage, and amenities. A five-point Likert scale response was set to each of the three questions, coded by 1 as '*strongly agree*' to 5 as '*strongly disagree*'. These questions were used to assess the attitudinal responses of participants to the prisoner characteristic. Lower scores represent an attitude which opted for the removal of prisoners' rights (Silvia, 2003).

To assess the impact of prisoner characteristics influencing opinion, the 10 vignettes were split into five pairs each labelled with a different prisoner characteristic. Each section contained high or low levels of each characteristic. Shown below are the vignettes used for prisoner behaviours. A full list of the vignettes used can be found in Appendix 8.1.

Question 10: “This prisoner has been sentenced to life in prison after being found guilty of multiple crimes (murder and attempted murder). During their sentence they have completed a higher education degree, actively worked with multiple charities, volunteered with youths attempting to deter them from criminal behaviours, and is active within the religious prison community. They have also been to multiple individual therapy sessions and group therapy sessions.”

Question 11: “This prisoner has been sentenced to life in prison due to multiple crimes committed (murder and manslaughter). During their sentence they have instigated multiple prison fights, caused physical harm to other prisoners, and prison officers. They have been moved to multiple prisons due to their disruptive behaviour. This prisoner does not engage with any available therapy, education, or charity work.”

When selecting the prisoner characteristics for the content of the vignettes, considerations towards previous academic findings, international prisoner rights law, and proposed UK government legislation were taken into account. These findings were then collated, refined, and reviewed. The final chosen prisoner categories were behaviour in prison (Q10, 11), severity of convicted crime (Q12, 13), prison sentence length (Q14, 15), age of offender (Q16, 17), and number of previous convicted crimes (Q18, 19). Each of these characteristics are related to previous studies finding that interpersonal characteristics of prisoners directly tie to leniency towards sentencing, influence on public opinion, or display the current national laws of prisoner rights (Roberts and Hough, 2013; Belton and Dhimi, 2024). The characteristic was placed into the vignette description in slightly differing ways attempting to not reveal the research intention and create a bias in answers (Barter and Renold, 1999).

During the creation of the vignette content, real-life examples were taken from the Crown Prosecution Service (CPS) to reflect real judicial decisions. The CPS News Centre (2024) was the main webpage used to find content for the vignettes. The webpage contains CPS press releases detailing recent criminal proceedings and outcomes from Crown courts over England and Wales. Only press releases published in 2023 or 2024 were used to maintain accuracy and validity in the example vignettes. Identifying factors from the press released cases were also removed to decrease any personal bias from the participants.

Utilising case studies from real trials enhances experimental realism of the study and increase internal and external validity (Aguinis and Bradley, 2014). To be successful, the content of vignettes needs to be easily understood but not too specific as to give away the questions intention to the participants (Barter and Renold, 1999). To assess the reliability of the responses from the prisoner vignettes, each participant was also asked a series of questions about the specific prisoner characteristics *without* added context. For example, Q10 and Q11 (shown above) contained descriptions with variations in prisoner behaviours which relates to Q22 which reads: *'Do you think that a prisoner's ability to vote in political elections should be earned through good behaviour?'*. By including questions asking about the characteristic directly, it allows participants to clearly understand the content of the question without extra added information from a vignette which may unintentionally bias their answer (Barter and Renold, 1999).

2.3.4 Prior knowledge

Utilising the limitations of previous prisoner disenfranchisement academic studies, it was revealed that there was a general lack of understanding as to the reliability of public knowledge (Dhami and Cruise, 2013; Roberts and Hough, 2005). Therefore, this study aimed to address these shortcomings by asking participants about current and proposed prisoner rights policy. This aids in assessing the validity of the sample through such questions as, *'Did you know that convicted prisoners in England and Wales are currently unable to vote in political elections?'* (Appendix 8.1). This information will add to the understanding of the general level of knowledge of prisoner rights matters. Furthermore, this data can be applicable for exploring a link between the accuracy of knowledge and opinions on prisoner rights.

2.4 Data preparation

Prior to exporting the data from Online Surveys, two sets of responses had to be excluded from the final sample. One discounted response was the result of a pilot test. The pilot test was undertaken on the first version of the survey to test spelling, grammar, and the overall appeal of the survey (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). The second response excluded from the final data set was done so due to offensive language and unserious answers from open-text box responses. It was therefore decided to remove this response to ensure the reliability of the sample results. All remaining data was then exported from Online Surveys into an SPSS file and Microsoft Excel file in preparation for analysis.

2.5 Analytic strategy

Analysing the main data findings within this study was done using SPSS Statistics. Demographic frequencies were taken from the data including age and gender. This data was assessed using a crosstabulation method to view the demographic within the sample (Table 1). The largest sample demographic was females (N= 32), and those aged 18-25 (N=29), and the smallest was males (N=21), and those aged 36-45 (N=2).

Crosstabulation: Gender and age

Count		How old are you?				Total
		18-25	26-35	36-45	46+	
How would you identify your gender?	Male	11	1	0	9	21
	Female	18	5	2	7	32
Total		29	6	2	16	53

Table 2 – Gender and age of sample

For the main body of findings, a dependant t-test was the most appropriate analysis method due to the categorised repeated measures design of the survey. Before analysing the data, it was checked through the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality due to the small sample size (Field, 2013). However, the data was shown to be non-normally distributed, *Sig.<0.05* (Appendix 8.2). Regardless of this failed assumption, the dependent t-test remained the chosen data analysis method due to the type of data collected and the time remit of the dissertation. Therefore, it must be considered within any findings that the input data is non- normally distributed.

The dependent t-test analysis was carried out for all of the five pairs of prisoner characteristic vignettes. Each pair of vignettes was separated further by the prisoner right being questioned (voting and marriage) to understand any potential significant results from a specific prisoner right. The significance rate was set at 0.05 to show a 95% confidence rate. The dependent t-test was examined using the equation $t(df)=t,p=0.05$. Data from supporting questions asking prior knowledge of prisoner rights and opinions were cross tabulated using the count, mean, and percentage of results. Likert scale responses were coded on a scale of 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). Any interesting data was examined, and any connections to the main set of data was explored.

Research into public opinions and attitudes aids in supporting quantitative findings with qualitative data. Utilising a mixed-method data collection, it allows for triangulation in which both types of data

can identify themes and patterns that relate to the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). As the qualitative data collected was intended as supportive data, thematic analysis was chosen due to its flexible and accessible nature as an analytic method (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This was done using Braun and Clarke's (2006) 6-step thematic analysis.

The qualitative dataset was exported from Online Surveys to a Microsoft Excel file. Each set of qualitative answers was individually moved across to a Microsoft Word document to more clearly understand and code the findings. Braun and Clarke's (2006) 6-step thematic analysis was used on each set of answers. This included becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, identifying themes, and writing up the findings (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). This process allowed a more thorough understanding of the data and created a supporting system of themes to use alongside the main body of findings.

2.6 Ethical considerations

Ethical approval from Loughborough University was gained for the content of the study (Appendix 8.5). The methodological approach of online surveys is integral to the design of this study, therefore certain parameters must be considered for ethical concerns that arise using this type of methodology (Buchanan and Hvizdak, 2008). Ethical considerations such as sensitive content and participant consent were combated by purposeful design choices in the survey.

Informed consent was required from each participant before taking part in the study (Appendix 8.1). A description of the study informed participants of the nature of the study, as well as informing them that their data would remain anonymous. Contact information of the primary researcher was provided for participants to communicate any concerns, exclude their answers if they wish, or provide feedback for the survey content. Sensitive content was considered when designing the prisoner vignettes. To ensure content of the vignettes was suitable for the audience, the vignette content was directly taken from real example cases available publicly from the CPS. Alongside improving ecological validity (Aguinis and Bradley, 2014), using publicly available resources ensures further protection for the sample; pre-checks for published media are mandatory for content from the CPS reducing potentially distressing details of criminal acts.

2.7 Pilot test

Before the launch of the survey, a pilot test was conducted to assess certain aspects of the questionnaire; checking spelling, accessibility of wording, accurate completion time, and

questions/answers were collecting the intended data. This was crucial to ensure that the questionnaire was appropriate for the sample, and to finalise mistakes that could cause an incomplete dataset (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001). The test data was excluded from the final dataset.

The pilot test revealed several errors including incorrect spelling, duplicated questions, and the vignettes not being universally accessible and required specialist knowledge to fully understand. An amended survey draft was completed in which the feedback was applied by removing duplicate questions, fixing spelling errors, and altering the wording of the vignettes. The inaccessibility from the vignettes was mainly due to the specialist language used, therefore the convictions taken from the CPS example cases were removed from the main body of the vignette text and replaced with a description. For example, Q18 previously read '*...this prisoner's previous convictions and imprisonments include possession of Class C drugs, conspiracy to supply Class C drugs, and reckless driving*' and changed to '*...this prisoner has multiple convictions, and over 5 years previous prison time*'. By utilising a pilot study, it created a valuable insight into the study from the participants viewpoint and aided in the development of a more reliable research protocol (Van Teijlingen and Hundley, 2001).

Chapter 3: Findings and discussion

3.1 Introduction

The predominant aims from this study were to investigate public opinion on prisoner rights, explore if these opinions were maintained in a contextualised situation, and if prisoner characteristics influenced views on prisoner rights. The findings will use contemporary arguments to understand these aims, focusing on how interpersonal prisoner characteristics lead to changes in the samples opinions and attitudes on prisoner rights. It must be noted that the data was pre-analysed using Shapiro-Wilk test of normality, and this sample consisted of non-normally distributed data (Appendix 8.2). This must be taken into consideration in the findings as normally distributed data may produce different results. The data sets were compared, and the results were interpreted in the context of existing literature and theories in the subject field.

The findings from this study have been separated into several themes of prisoner rights. Utilising a mixed-method data collection, triangulation allowed for a greater insight into the opinions and attitudes found within the data. Throughout the analysis there were commonalities found overlapping in each prisoner right studied (voting, marriage).

Therefore, it was decided to approach the findings section as how prisoner rights are perceived as a collective, rather than separate issues. One of the key findings in the results of this study, in line with previous findings, is the polarising public views towards prisoner rights (Dhami and Cruise, 2013; Easton, 2013; Jones and Davies, 2022).

3.2 Prisoner characteristics and the right to vote

This section will discuss the main analysis of this study which focused on whether prisoner characteristics are influential in public attitudes on prisoner voting rights, and exploring whether attitudes found are maintained when considering the wider characteristics of individual situations.

All prisoner characteristic pairs were analysed using the equation $t(df)=t,p=0.05$ using a significance rate of 0.05 to indicate a 95% confidence rate. It was determined within analysis that there was a statistically significant difference in three of the five prisoner characteristics: age $t(52)=2.360,p=0.022$, severity of convicted crime $t(52)=2.520, p=0.015$, and previous crimes $t(52)=3.292,p=0.002$ (Table 3). This shows that the sample were statistically more likely to change their attitude towards a prisoner's

voting right due to the prisoners age, number of previous convictions, or severity of convicted crime.

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Paired Differences		t	df	Significance		
				Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			One-Sided p	Two-Sided p	
				Lower	Upper					
Pair 1	Age: Old – young adult	.250	.764	.106	.037	.463	2.360	51	.011	.022
Pair 2	Severity of crime: violent – non-violent	.283	.818	.112	.058	.508	2.520	52	.007	.015
Pair 3	Previous convictions: None – multiple	.302	.668	.092	.118	.486	3.292	52	<.001	.002

Table 3 – Dependent t-test significant results: Attitudes on prisoner voting rights and prisoner interpersonal characteristics.

3.2.1 Younger prisoners should be able to vote

Results from the dependent t-test analysis showed a significant difference in the group pairing of prisoner age in attitudes on prisoner voting rights ($t(52)=2.360, p=0.022$). Interestingly, the sample of this study had a stronger leniency to the young-adult prisoner ($M=3.22$, coded to *Neither agree nor disagree*), compared to the old-aged prisoner ($M=2.84$, coded to *Disagree*) for their voting rights. However, it must be noted that the mean difference of 0.42 is not significant in the coding of the answer scales of ± 1 . Although the relationship between prisoner age and public opinion may seem inconclusive, it is important for the explanatory value of this study to investigate the potential meanings behind the sample response for this characteristic.

The findings from this study support the idea of an age-leniency effect (Blowers and Doerner, 2013) in which the extra-legal characteristics of an offender impacts punitive attitudes towards the offender. However, these results display the effect working in an opposite way than found originally; this sample showed a higher leniency towards the younger prisoner over old. More punitive attitudes towards older prisoners may be linked to the portrayal of older prisoners as being more likely to be convicted of historic offences (Trotter and Baidawi, 2014); which are often strongly linked to sex or child sex offences reported long after they were committed (Shead, 2018). This could suggest older prisoners are being homogenised into a ‘dangerous other’ as suggested by Drake (2011, p.1), of prolific historical sexual offenders, and the removal of voting rights is viewed as an additional punishment for these offenders. This is supported further by thematic results which revealed participants viewed the removal of voting rights as a consequence of criminal behaviours (Appendix 8.3).

In contrast, the sample may have shown more leniency towards the younger prisoner due to a close age proximity. The younger prisoner in the vignette was aged 20 years old and this sample contained

53.8% of participants aged 18-25 years. Working in direct contrast to the othering of prisoners, fundamental similarities between individuals lessen the chances of out-group rejection (Silvia et al, 2005). Therefore, closeness in age could elicit feelings of similarity thus leading to a more positive response to the younger prisoner. Furthermore, this age category had minimal personal connection, via family or friends, to prisoners (N=4, 13.8% of total). This reduces the chance of this sample showing a preference to the younger prisoner vignette due to real life connections with a prisoner/s. Overall, these findings would suggest that a further in-depth examination with a more representative sample is needed to understand if there is a strong association with prisoner age and public opinion on prisoner voting rights.

3.2.2 Prisoners that commit violent offences or have multiple previous convictions should forfeit their voting rights

The violence of a committed crime and the number of prior convictions from prisoners in the vignettes was statistically significant in its influence on the opinion of the sample ($t(52) = 2.520, p < 0.015$ and $t(52) = 3.292, p < 0.002$ respectively). Delving into the analysis further, the sample showed a preference towards the prisoner with no prior convictions (M=3.23 coded to *Neither agree nor disagree*) and the prisoner who had committed a non-violent crime (M=3.25, coded to *Neither agree nor disagree*). Similarly to the prisoner characteristic of age, the mean of these characteristics had a difference of 0.31 (type of crime) and 0.29 (prior convictions) which was not significant in the coding of the scaled answers of ± 1 .

Inconsistencies in the results could suggest that differences in participant attitudes may be attributed to gender. Both prisoner characteristics had a gender disparity in response, with female participants holding slightly more punitive attitudes to the more severe pairing than males (multiple previous crimes, and violent offence). Males in the sample showed no differences throughout each of the 4 vignettes. The mean view of the females in this sample was in favour of the prisoner with the non-violent offence (NVO: M=2.84, SD=1.43, VO: M=3.34, SD=1.53) and no previous crimes (NPC: M=2.84, SD=1.46, PC: M=3.34, SD=1.47). Although this finding does not hold significance in the scaled rating of ± 1 as the mean difference is 0.5 for both characteristics, the gender difference must still be noted. As previous research has found violent and physically harmful offences elicit more punitive responses from the public (Rossi and Berk, 1997), especially in female respondents (Chen and Einat, 2014) this would line up with the findings from this research. However, the sample contains majority females (59.6% N=31) and a very small sample base, therefore the reliability and generalisability of these findings is questionable.

In contrast, inconsistent results may be an indicator that participants were unclear about the prisoner characteristic they were responding to in the vignettes. It could be assumed that the vignette content may have been too broad, a common finding in vignette research (Barter and Renold, 1999). This may have led participants to miss the independent variable or attribute it to the wrong characteristic. The prisoner vignette from the multiple previous crimes pairing included “over 5 years previous prison time (including possession of Class C drugs, conspiracy to supply Class C drugs, and reckless driving)”, alongside the crime type vignette which included a prisoner sentenced for murder and grievous bodily harm (Appendix 8.1). Both examples describe the prisoner committing multiple crimes; therefore, participants may have answered to this effect rather than the intended characteristics of previous crimes and seriousness of crime. If the distinction between pairs was not clear enough it could have led participants to wrongly associate the differentiations of the prisoner characteristics.

Moreover, each prisoner’s sentence length was also listed in each vignette which may have influenced the results. This could suggest that responses to these prisoner characteristics may have differed if each vignette varied in their content rather than following a rigid structure. This is further supported by analysis showing no statistical significance from prisoner sentence length on attitudes towards prisoner voting rights ($t(51) = 0.830, p = 0.411$). Therefore, the content of vignettes not communicating effectively to participants may have caused bias in the responses, leading to outcomes that may not match true attitudes.

3.3 All prisoners should have their voting rights removed

Certain prisoner characteristics were found to accept the null hypothesis by showing no impact on opinions towards prisoner voting rights. Table 4 displays two out of the five prisoner characteristics showed no statistical significance in the dependent t-test: behaviour in prison and sentence length ($t(52) = -1.660, p = 0.103$ and $t(51) = 0.83, p = 0.411$ respectively).

		Paired Differences				t	df	Significance	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower Upper			One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
Pair 1	Behaviour in prison: Good – Bad	-.151	.662	.091	-.333 .032	-1.660	52	.051	.103
Pair 2	Sentence length: Long – Short	.058	.502	.070	-.082 .197	.830	51	.205	.411

Table 4 – Dependent t-test results: Attitudes on prisoner voting rights and prisoner interpersonal characteristics.

One surprising characteristic that accepted the null hypothesis was prisoners with good (M=3.06 coded to *Neither agree nor disagree*) or bad (M=2.91 coded to *Disagree*) behaviours. This was interesting as existing literature in this subject field has shown public support to the idea of behaviour controlling prisoner's rights (Booth, 2020; Easton, 2013). Utilising thematic findings, participants expressed support for the idea of prisoners forfeiting their right to vote because of their imprisonment, rather than a privilege that could be earned through good behaviour (Appendix 8.3). These results display an influence of othering by indicating that a prisoner's ability to access their voting rights should be restricted due to their status as a prisoner. However, utilising previous findings from the vignettes, this sample does not view *all* prisoners as a homogenous other. These combined results display a defined preference for specific interpersonal characteristics of prisoners. Furthermore, the results present an opposed argument to a well-established finding in existing literature in which the public show a preference for well-behaved prisoners (Booth, 2020). However, these results must be taken with caution as due to the non-normally distributed data and the small sample size, this result cannot be accurately representative of public views. Nonetheless, it creates an avenue of exploration into critiquing the importance of prisoner behaviours in public views on prisoner rights.

Turning now to the other prisoner characteristic that accepted the null hypothesis: sentence length. This characteristic is a common parameter for international prisoner voting rights, such as the current framework used in Australia (Thorne and White, 2015; Hill, 2009). However, the findings from this study oppose these policies in action as the analysis showed no significance for the characteristic of sentence length (Table 4). Furthermore, taking into consideration the significant findings for the three prisoner characteristics (age, severity of crime committed, and number of previous crimes), it suggests that the parameters for prisoner voting legislation is focused on the wrong aspect. By creating an alternate system of operationalising characteristics that deem a prisoner eligible to vote, it could inadvertently have a criminogenic influence on those who fall outside the threshold. Some prisoners would still face the same invisible punishment of disenfranchisement as today and would feel less inclined to get involved in a democracy that doesn't 'recognise the prisoner as a citizen' (Easton, 2013, p.489). Therefore, applying these results into a policy context needs to be handled with care.

3.4 Prisoner characteristics and the right to marriage

This section will discuss prisoner characteristics that influenced opinions on a prisoner’s right to marriage. Results displayed difference in attitudes between the prisoner rights of voting and marriage. The dependent t-test analysis showed a statistically significant difference in attitudes towards four out of the five prisoner characteristics: Behaviour in prison ($t(51) = -3.503, p < 0.05$), severity of convicted crime ($t(52) = 3.922, p < 0.05$), prison sentence length ($t(52) = 2.57, p < 0.05$), and number of previous crimes ($t(52) = 2.49, p < 0.05$) (Table 5). In combination with results from the opinion question ‘Do you think prisoners serving life sentences should be able to get married?’ the sample displayed a preference (67.9%, N=36) for allowing life-sentenced prisoners the right to get married.

Dependent t-test significant results: Opinions on prisoner marriage rights and interpersonal prisoner characteristics

		Paired Differences					t	df	Significance	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				One-Sided p	Two-Sided p
					Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Behaviour: Good – Bad	-.423	.871	.121	-.666	-.181	-3.503	51	<.001	<.001
Pair 2	Nature of crime: Non-violent – violent	.415	.770	.106	.203	.627	3.922	52	<.001	<.001
Pair 3	Sentence length: Short – Long	.151	.411	.056	.038	.264	2.672	52	.005	.010
Pair 4	Previous convictions: Multiple – None	.170	.509	.070	.030	.310	2.429	52	.009	.019

Table 5 – Dependent t-test significant results: Attitudes on prisoner marriage rights and prisoner interpersonal characteristics.

Exploring these findings further, results indicate more punitive attitudes are held towards a prisoner that is poorly behaved in prison (M=2.79 coded to *Disagree*), has committed a violent offence (M=2.72 coded to *Disagree*), has a longer sentence length (M=2.75 coded to *Disagree*), and has multiple previous crimes (M=2.77 coded to *Disagree*). Compared to the 67.9% (N=36) of participants who said all prisoners should have the right to marriage, this indicates that contextual details of an individual prisoner can seemingly change attitudes towards a prisoner’s right to marriage.

3.4.1 Links to policy implementation

These findings directly link to the government action set out by the Victims and Prisoners Bill 2023 in which life-sentenced prisoners will have their right to marriage revoked. So far, there has been no public consultation regarding the content of the bill and this study aims to fill this gap by researching public views of the removal of a prisoner’s right to marriage. The potential removal of this right has caused concern from victims and prisoner rights charities alike (Foxwell, 2023; Prison Reform Trust, 2023) due

to infringements on a prisoner’s human rights as set out in the ECHR (European Court of Human Rights, 2022). Thematic analysis results from this study support the concerns raised as participants recognise the rehabilitative significance that marriage and partnership may hold for prisoners (Appendix 8.4). However, further analysis from the dependent t-test results shows the sample favoured the refusal of a prisoner’s marriage right for specific prisoners. Thus, these results suggest the sample viewed the right to marriage as a right that holds significant value, yet attitudinal responses indicate prisoner characteristics are influential in the implementation of this right. Overall, these findings cannot directly facilitate a pro- or anti-prisoner marriage right public stance. This thereby suggests that further and more specific research would enhance the understanding of public opinions towards a prisoner’s right to marriage, and the true impact of this bill.

3.4.2 Participant age is an indicator of punitive opinions on a prisoner’s right to marriage

Attempting to understand these inconsistencies further, Table 6 displays the participant age split of opinions on prisoner’s marriage right. Pro-prisoner rights opinions were held strongest by those aged 18-25 (63% of ‘Yes’ answer, N=23/36), and the highest disenfranchisement opinions were held by participants aged 46+ (58.8% of ‘No’ answer, N=10/17).

Crosstabulation: Age and opinion on prisoner marriage rights

Do you think prisoners serving life sentences should be able to get married?

		Yes		No		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
How old are you?	18-25	23	63.9%	6	35.3%	29	54.7%
	26-35	6	16.7%	0	0.0%	6	11.3%
	36-45	1	2.8%	1	5.9%	2	3.8%
	46+	6	16.7%	10	58.8%	16	30.2%
Total		36	100.0%	17	100.0%	53	100.0%

Table 6 – Sample age and opinion on prisoner marriage rights

These results indicate an age difference in punitive opinions which supports findings in previous research (Payne et al, 2004). However, rather than being solely related to prisoner characteristics these findings may also reflect the way marriage is viewed in society. With an increasingly secularised society leading to less reliance on marriage as a traditional rite of passage or symbol of status (Auchmuty, 2012; Walliss, 2002) the significance of marriage is lessening in the newer generations (Gubernskaya, 2010). The findings of this study could be a display of these theoretical constructs rather than punitiveness towards prisoners.

Furthermore, this may also be a factor in explaining differences in the opinion and attitudinal responses of this sample. As marriage is viewed as less important in younger generations, which represents 53.8% (N=28) of this sample, this ideology could be placed onto a prisoner's right to marriage as having no social significance if not *fulfilled* but holds significance if not *accessible*. However, this study did not ask participants their personal view on marriage therefore the inferences made must be taken with caution.

3.5 Should all prisoners have rights?

This section will discuss the sample's perception and knowledge of prisoner rights without added situational context. A key aspect of this study was exploring public opinion on prisoner rights; therefore, it was important to gather this information without potential bias from the vignette content. The findings from this section will be discussed further in relation to the previous established findings and existing literature in the subject field.

3.5.1 All prisoners should have the right to vote

The opinion of this sample showed a preference for the enfranchisement of prisoners (65.4%) which is an uncommon finding in previous public opinion studies (Easton, 2013). Figure 3 displays out of a total 52 participants, 65.4% (N=34) voted 'yes' on question 5 'Do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?', and 34.6% (N=18) voted No. A mean rank of 1.35 (SD=0.48), from nominal measures applied to answers of Yes as 1, and No as 2 was found.

Figure 3 – opinions on prisoner voting rights

It must be noted that the sample of 53 respondents in this study is not large enough to be representative of public views towards prisoner rights. However, analysis into the sample demographics

showed that participant occupations could be a factor towards discrepancies in results (Chen and Einat, 2014). This sample contains 29% (N=15) students which compared to the general population in the UK of 4% students, there is an over-representation of this occupation (Bolton, 2024). Moreover, 15% (N=8) of the sample had occupations involved with the CJS in some capacity; examples include prison officer, probation officer, and student police officer (Appendix 8.6). This aligns with previous research findings that criminology/criminal justice students (Tsoudis, 2000) and police officers have less punitive attitudes towards prisoner punishment (Chen and Einat, 2014). As participants were recruited utilising a snowball sample technique, it is likely that student participants will be undertaking a criminology degree, however this inference must be taken with caution as this study did not gather this information.

3.5.2 Participant age is an indicator of opinions on prisoner rights

Participant age was found to be an indicator of punitive opinions towards prisoner voting rights from this sample. The youngest age demographic from this sample, aged 18-25 (N=28, 53.8% of total), accounted for 42.3% (N=22) of ‘yes’ answers from question 5 ‘Do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?’ (Table 7). However, it must be considered that this age demographic was the largest (53.8%) of the sample base.

Furthermore, the occupations in this age category included all the students in the sample (N=15), and 75% of the CJS occupations (N=6/8). In line with previous research, these occupations were found to have less punitive attitudes towards prisoners (Chen and Einat, 2014). Therefore, when taking into consideration these factors it is unsurprising that this age group displays a less punitive opinion overall.

Age and opinion on prisoner voting rights
Do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?

		Yes		No		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
How old are you?	18-25	22	64.7%	6	33.3%	28	53.8%
	26-35	4	11.8%	2	11.1%	6	11.5%
	36-45	1	2.9%	1	5.6%	2	3.8%
	46+	7	20.6%	9	50.0%	16	30.8%
Total		34	100.0%	18	100.0%	52	100.0%

Table 7 – Sample age an opinion on prisoner voting rights

Furthermore, results from this question show the oldest age group in this sample (46+) displayed the highest disenfranchisement opinion (50% of total ‘no’ response, N=9, Figure 4). This finding may be due to personal political opinions related to age. Previous research into voting behaviours has shown older

voters are more likely to vote for the Conservative party (Johnson et al, 2018) which prioritises harsher more punitive penal policies in line with a ‘tough on crime’ approach (Newburn, 2007). However, it cannot be certain as this study did not ask participants about their political views. In contrast, an alternate reason for an increase in punitive attitudes for the 46+ participant group may be caused by a fear of victimisation (Age UK, 2019), or viewing an increased amount of media reporting of serious crimes (Roberts and Hough, 2005). However, more recent data from the Office for National Statistics (2024) has shown younger age categories (16-24) are more likely to be victims of crime which casts doubt onto the reliability of these findings. The results of this study show that age can be an indicator of punitive opinions towards prisoner voting rights, however the combination of extra factors must be taken into consideration when determining the strength of this relationship.

Figure 4 – Sample age and opinion on prisoner voting right

3.5.3 Males showed a more punitive opinion for prisoner rights

Examining the potential driving factors behind certain views on prisoner rights, the gender of participants was analysed alongside participant opinion. Previous research has found men have more punitive responses to prisoners and criminal punishment than women (Haghighi and Lopez, 1998). These finding will be analysed with this sample to understand the applicability of gender disparity for opinions on prisoner rights.

Participants had gender options in the online survey of female, male, non-binary, or an open textbox in which they could express their gender freely. All accepted responses self- identified as either female or

male. The sample consisted of 40.4% males (N=21) and 59.6% females (N=31). When compared to the UK general population in 2021 of 51% females and 49% males (ONS, 2023), there is a slight increase in females in this sample. Therefore, due to the inconsistent gender proportions and small sample size, the results cannot be accurately representative of public views. However, findings will still be applied to relevant research in the academic field.

Gender and prisoner voting rights opinion

		How would you identify your gender?					
		Male		Female		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?	Yes	13	61.9%	21	67.7%	34	65.4%
	No	8	38.1%	10	32.3%	18	34.6%
Total		21	100.0%	31	100.0%	52	100.0%

Table 8 – Sample gender and opinion on prisoner voting rights

Table 8 shows the answers from question 5 ‘do you think prisoners should be able to vote in political elections?’ applied to participant gender. In this sample, men were shown to have a more punitive opinion towards prisoner voting rights than women, relative to the participant gender group. Results showed that 38.1% (N=8) of male participants compared to 32.3% (N=10) of female participants voted *No* for prisoners voting rights.

Previous findings in gender disparity and punitive attitudes have shown men to hold stronger punitive attitudes towards punishment than women (Haghighi and Lopez, 1998). However, Haghighi and Lopez (1998) noted that the intersectionality of class, race, and media consumption impacted these findings, and concluded gender may not be the deciding factor in punitive opinions towards prisoners. This could have impacted the findings from this study. However, participants were not asked about their class standing, race, or media consumption therefore it cannot be deductively concluded. Furthermore, contradicting results of the importance of gender in prisoner reform opinions was found by Silvia (2003) who found gender disparity in punitive attitudes research was overstated. The results from this study alongside accompanying findings suggest that further research would be needed to explore the relationship of gendered attitudes on prisoner rights. With the low numbers of responses from this study, it doesn’t allow for a generalised view to be placed on gendered demographics and their given opinions.

3.5.4 Supporting prisoner rights is more likely in those with accurate knowledge of prisoner right legislation

This section will explore if accurate knowledge of prisoner rights legislation influences opinions on the topic. Exploring this relationship, participants were asked about their knowledge on current and proposed prisoner rights policy (voting, marriage) in England and Wales. Results show a mixture of responses; the sample were mostly accurately informed about current prisoner voting rights (69.8% 'yes', $M=1.30$, $SD = 0.43$), however, mostly unaware of the change of prisoner marriage rights (90.6% 'no', $M=1.91$, $SD=0.29$). By comparing participant knowledge to their opinion on these rights, it allows exploration into the way public awareness of prisoner rights can influence opinions towards them.

Discussing this disparity, the graph on Figure 5 shows 81% ($N=13/16$) of participants that did not know about current prisoner voting rights thought that prisoners *should* have the right to vote. Furthermore, this finding is supported by the results from prisoner marriage rights shown on Figure 6; 86.1% ($N=31/36$) of participants did not know about the proposed removal of this right yet thought prisoners *should* have the right for marriage. These results indicate that knowledge of prisoner rights is a contributing factor towards public support in prisoner rights discourse. The inconsistency found between prior knowledge and current opinion shows a gap of potential support of the prisoner rights movement. Prisoner right charities could utilise this finding by improving public knowledge of the 'invisible punishment' (Dhami and Cruise, 2013, p.1) prisoners go through when their rights are removed in prison. This could lead to increased levels of support for the protection of rights for prisoners alongside the ECHR. However, to successfully implement change, the obstacle of othering of prisoners would need to be overcome. To reduce out-group rejection, pointing out similarities between the public and prisoners could reduce the idea of a negative homogenous prisoner group (Silvia et al, 2003).

Figure 5 – Prior knowledge and current opinion (Voting rights)

Figure 6 – Prior knowledge and current opinion (Marriage rights)

Using previous findings from the vignettes, prisoner characteristics such as age, type of crime committed, and previous crimes could be utilised to individualise prisoners and create public support for prisoner rights. An outcome of public support for prisoner rights would aid in fighting against an anti-prisoner rhetoric (Dhami, 2005), and allow prisoners to fulfil their human rights as set out in the ECHR.

3.6 Limitations and future recommendations

Although this study fills a gap in current research by exploring the relationship between prisoner characteristics and public views of prisoner disenfranchisement, there are study limitations which will be examined.

Sample size and demographic from this sample are not representative of a 'public' sample. The gender ratio overrepresents female participants, which differs from current gender demographics in the UK (Office for National Statistics, 2023). Furthermore, the sample size (N=52) is too small to be representative of public views. Due to limited time and resources from this dissertation, the survey did not reach a large enough audience to combat these limitations. Therefore, due to the discrepancies within the current sample, future research would benefit from reaching a wider audience to gather more reliable representative results of public opinion. However, it must be noted that the sample in this study was larger than the public sample gathered by the British government when informing the changes to prisoner disenfranchisement policy (Thorne and White, 2015). Thereby enabling meaningful conclusions to be drawn from the data.

A further issue with this study is the choice of data analysis. The data was found to be non-normally distributed from a Shapiro-Wilk test of normality (Appendix 8.2). Therefore, a non-parametric analysis such as a Wilcoxon signed-rank test could have been used (Field, 2009) rather than a dependent t-test. Further study may benefit from utilising other statistical analysis options such as ANOVA with normally distributed data, or Wilcoxon signed-rank with non-normally distributed data. However, due to the repeated measures design of this study and the time parameters from the dissertation, a dependent t-test was chosen as the most suitable option.

Chapter 4: Conclusion

The present study aimed to investigate 1) public opinions on prisoner rights, 2) if these opinions were maintained in practice in contextualised situations, and 3) if specific characteristics of prisoners influenced these opinions. Findings displayed a majority pro-prisoner enfranchisement sample base; however, this was not maintained in contextualised situations. A relationship between prisoner characteristics and opinions on prisoner rights was found, and distinct characteristics were linked to different opinions on prisoner rights.

This dissertation provides a nuanced view into current opinions on prisoner rights, a study topic that is often ignored in favour of continuing prisoner disenfranchisement as a further punishment for criminal behaviour. Utilising the limitations and recommendations of previous studies, important relationships such as accurate knowledge and sample demographics were explored in relation to prisoner rights opinions. These relationships demonstrated that an accurate knowledge base is key in supporting the enfranchisement of prisoners. Additionally, these findings can be utilised by prisoner rights charities and outreach groups to improve the support base for prisoner rights, ensuring that their human rights remain intact even whilst imprisoned.

The findings from this dissertation provide a unique insight into the interpersonal prisoner characteristics that hold weighting in opinions and attitudes of prisoner rights, and fills a gap in research by investigating the impact that othering has on views on prisoner rights. Although, previous research has explored public views on prisoner disenfranchisement, it fails to understand how individual prisoner circumstances influence views in relation to access to their rights. Utilising the discussion in this study, each prisoner right was influenced by different individual prisoner characteristics. This suggests that prisoner characteristics may be instrumental in settling the public discourse surrounding prisoner rights. However, applying these findings into a realistic situation creates difficulty. As the parameters between each prisoner characteristic and prisoner right are unique, creating a one-size-fits-all approach becomes a laborious task. The negative othering of prisoners has become common practice, and the results of this study display the detrimental impact this can have on prisoner rights. By individualising prisoners, it reduces the 'dangerous other' portrayal of prisoners (Drake, 2011).

The current investigation provides an insight into this research gap. Although the findings do not provide entirely significant results, as explained in the results and study limitations sections, it

emphasises the importance of individualising prisoners. Previous studies have highlighted how human rights have become rebranded as prisoner rights (Dhami and Cruise, 2013) and this study aims to bring further awareness to this.

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